

FINANCIAL DISCLOSURE IN CORPORATE ANNUAL REPORTS : A SURVEY OF SELECTED LITERATURE

Rubina Maleque*
Farhana Rahman**
Alim Al Ayub Ahmed***

Abstract : The topic of disclosure is broad enough to encompass almost the entire area of financial reporting. One of the major objectives of financial reporting is to supply information for decision-making. This requires a proper disclosure of financial data and other relevant information. Disclosure is vital for the optimum decisions of investors and for a stable capital market. Timely disclosure of relevant information tends to prevent surprises that may completely alter the outlook for the future of the firm. It also tends to give investors greater confidence in the financial information available to them. The relevant studies are reviewed here focusing their objectives, methodology followed, hypothesis tested, concluding remarks, and limitations thereon.

1. Introduction

Proper disclosure of relevant information in the financial statements of a company is of great importance, since the members of the company as well as other parties; make most of their appraisals regarding the company on the basis of such statements. Annual financial statements should, therefore, disclose relevant financial information clearly and accurately.

Disclosure in financial reporting is the presentation of information necessary for the optimum operation of efficient capital markets. This implies that sufficient information should be presented to permit the prediction of future dividend trends and variability and the co variability of future returns with the market. Emphasis should be placed on the preferences of sophisticated investors and financial analysts. "The ultimate objective of disclosure is to communicate timely, reliable, and material information which is useful to the users of annual reports, in an intelligible form." (Agarwal, 1995)

How much information should be disclosed is dependent not only upon the expertise of the reader, but also upon the desirable standard. Three concepts of disclosure generally proposed are adequate, fair and full disclosure. The most commonly used of these expressions is adequate disclosure. But this implies a minimum amount of disclosure congruous with the negative objective of making the

*Associate Professor, Dept. of Management, Dhaka University.

** Lecturer, Dept. of Marketing, Stamford University, Dhaka.

***Assistant Professor (Accounting), ASA University Bangladesh.

statements not misleading. Fair and full are more positive concepts. Fair disclosure implies an ethical objective of providing equal treatment for all potential reader. Full disclosure implies the presentation of all relevant information. To some, full disclosure means the presentation of superfluous information and is therefore inappropriate.

2. Corporate Annual Reports as a Device of Information Disclosure

Disclosure means effective communication of meaningful information. Disclosure is concerned with providing information, which are useful in making business and economic decisions by the audience-of-interest and the parties who have right to receive it. Financial disclosure is the end output of the financial reporting process. The balance sheet, profit and loss account and cash flow statement along with the supporting notes are known as the basic financial disclosure. Accounting may be treated as an information system that needs financial statements as the end result. Financial statements are the summarized and classified reports of financial events.

In a greater sense, financial statements are the direct product of a large number of integrated accounting processes which provide periodic income, financial position and cash flow statements (Mueller and Kelly: 1991).

All financial statements is concerned in varying degrees with decision-making. The need for disclosure to audience-of-interest on which to base investment, credit and similar decisions underlie the objectives of financial reporting. The importance of disclosure must be evaluated in relation to the purposes to be served, and the objectives of disclosure are focused in the use of accounting disclosure in decision-making.

The International Accounting Standards Committee (IASC) describes financial statements in its Exposure Draft-28, Framework for the preparation and presentation of Financial Statements, as

"Financial statements normally include a balance sheet, a profit and loss statement, a statement of changes in financial position, notes and other statements and explanatory material that are integral parts of the financial statements". (IASC, 1988)

The financial statements give information about an enterprise's resources, obligation and earnings. The purpose of financial statements is to give information that are useful to users in making managerial and economic decisions.

According to the definition given by the Accounting Standard Steering Committee (ASSC) of the UK and Ireland, a corporate financial report means "the comprehensive package of information of all kinds which describes an organization's economic activity"(1975).

Financial statements give useful information and detailed information is given by corporate financial reports although the information relates directly or indirectly to the information provided by a business enterprise's accounting system. In addition to basic financial statements, it provides narrative and descriptive statements and often-illustrative materials. Financial reporting is a means of providing information to users of all kinds, which most completely describes an organization's economic activity. It has also been stated that "... .. *Financial reporting by the entities attempts to meet the needs of the external users of financial reports who lack authority to prescribe the financial information they want from entities"* (FASB, 1978).

Financial reporting in broader terms not only includes financial statements but also other means of communicating information relating directly or indirectly to the information provided by the accounting system. A comprehensive financial report

may typically include corporate annual reports, various statutory annual information filing with regulatory commissions and registration statements for new securities to be sold publicly (Mueller and Kelly, 1991). Management may communicate information to those outside an enterprise by means other than the financial statement either because the information is required to be disclosed by authoritative pronouncement, regulatory rule or custom or because management considers it useful to those outside the enterprise and discloses it voluntarily.

3. Objectives of the Study

The primary objective of the study is to review of the selected literature regarding financial disclosure in corporate annual reports. The specific objective of this paper is to provide a short review of the main literature relevant to establish a research problem. A detailed review of the literature helps provide a framework for a broad study and serves the function of discovering findings from previous research on the general problem, helps establish what theories are relevant to the study being undertaken and assists in establishing an appropriate research methodology and research procedure to study the problem.

4. Review of Related Literature

4.1. Introduction

This section reviews researches that have focused primarily on information in corporate annual reports. Company financial reporting in the sub-continent has its origin in the Statutory Act of 1957. But a widespread research in this area is till now a matter of expectation in Bangladesh. Only some scholars have studied about financial reporting in the banking Sector in Bangladesh. A brief summary of these is delineated hereunder to prove the rationale of the present study.

During the last four decades the research literature on timeliness has become established in financial accounting. Different research studies have been done on the multidimensional aspects of financial reporting, disclosure policy, regulatory framework, harmonization of International Accounting Standards, application of local and International Accounting Standards in financial reporting practices of different multinational and local companies of different countries of the world. The relevant studies are reviewed here focusing their objectives, methodology followed, hypothesis tested, concluding remarks, and limitations thereon. This chapter reviews in detail selected studies that focus on financial disclosure in the corporate annual reports in both Bangladesh and abroad.

The literature survey is split as follows:

- Review of literature in Bangladesh Studies
- Review of Literature in Abroad Studies

4.2 Review of Related Study in Bangladesh

Studies in Bangladesh consider the multidimensional aspects relating to the disclosure in financial reporting. The following studies have reviewed:

Akter and Hoque (1993) have written an article on *"Disclosure Practices in Bangladesh: A Case Study of the Banking Sector"*. The objective of the study is to examine various legal provisions affecting disclosure along with role of the accounting profession in this respect. Recent trends and practices of reporting in the banking sector have been examined which facilitated presentation of the findings of this study in a framework of comparison and contrast.

This study is basically based on secondary data. This article has been prepared on the basis of review of existing literature relating to financial disclosure of banks. Relevant provisions and sections of the Banking Companies Ordinance as amended in 1991, Companies Act of 1913, Income Tax Ordinance of 1984 have been examined. To find out the present practice of the financial disclosure by banking companies in Bangladesh, annual reports of-

- i) one nationalised bank i.e., Sonali Bank,
- ii) one private bank City Bank, and
- iii) two multinational banks operating in Bangladesh i.e. American Express Bank and ANZ Grindlays Bank

have been analyzed for a period of five years (1987-91). To facilitate comparison, annual reports of three banks functioning in the developed countries like Citicorp Bank of the U.S.A., National Westminster Bank of U.K. and Chase Manhattan Bank of the U.S.A. have also been examined. This helps to find the recent trends and patterns of financial disclosure in the developed countries. Data have been presented in the framework of comparison and contrast. Other literature examined includes recommendation of International Accounting Standards Committee (IASC), research based articles published in the local and foreign journals, opinion of Accounting Principles Board (APB), Research monograph, books, etc. Data have been collected mainly from the secondary sources.

Compared to developed world, disclosure regarding loan valuation is very inadequate in the banking sector of Bangladesh. Special attention should be given for inadequate disclosure of specific provision, general provision, adjustment for exchange rate fluctuations, bad debt written off, transfer between provisions, charge against profit, sovereign risk provision etc., which are very important for measuring the efficiency and profitability of the banking sector.

This study reveals that disclosure and reporting in banking sector of Bangladesh are not only inadequate but also biased and misfiling. In most of the cases, financial statements of the local banks are dressed up and cosmetised. Outdated legal framework and poor performance of the accounting profession significantly contributed to this undesirable situation.

Ahmed and Nicholls (1994) have undertaken an empirical study to assess the extent of disclosure of statutory information in the corporate annual reports of non-financial companies and the impact of selected key company attributes on the degree of disclosure compliance with accounting regulatory statutes in a developing country, Bangladesh. They measured the association between the extent of disclosure and some corporate characteristics (size, total debt, multinational company effect, qualification of accountants and the size of the audit firm).

They collected 63 corporate annual reports available to them for the financial year 1987-1988. They developed an unweighted disclosure index. Their results indicated that like Nigeria and Hong Kong companies none of the companies in the sample from Bangladesh disclosed all mandatory items of information. Their results showed that the level of disclosure and both measures of company size, assets and sales, were positively associated. In addition, disclosure compliance was higher for a company which was a subsidiary of a multinational company and whose accounts were audited by a large audit firm, and whose accounts were prepared and supervised by a professionally qualified accountant. They suggested that for improvement in the degree of compliance, the accounting profession should strengthen its monitoring and enforcement mechanisms and increase awareness

about the existing mandatory provisions by conducting training programs for its members on a regular basis.

Islam and Pramanik (1996) have made a study on *"Disclosure of Accounting Policies: A Study of the Commercial Banks in Bangladesh"*. The main objective of the study is to evaluate disclosure practices relating to accounting policies of the commercial banks in Bangladesh. The present study covers a period of ten years based on published annual reports and relevant reports and relevant reporting requirements. The quality and adequacy of accounting policies have been analyzed from the viewpoint of the users of information. The observations give testimony that the banks under study tried to focus emphases on the professional requirements especially on IAS-1 as adopted in Bangladesh as AS-1 in making disclosure of accounting policies. But promulgation as to compliance with the professional requirements was absent from the annual reports. Another important finding was that despite several shortcomings observed in case of accounting policies of all the banks, the nationalized banks comparatively provided better disclosure of accounting policies than the private banks.

In the absence of specific legal requirements, disclosure practices relating to accounting policies of the commercial banks under study were complied during the study period, to a great extent, with the professional requirements especially with IAS-1 and this standard is adopted in Bangladesh as AS-1. But the disappointing finding was that promulgation as to compliance with the professional requirements was absent from the statement of accounting policies shown in the annual reports. This means that the professional requirements might be followed unconsciously or as a matter of convention. Although same sorts of accounting policies followed over the years facilitated uniformity, consistency and comparability of accounting information in case of each bank, the nationalized banks comparatively provided an enriched disclosure of accounting policies than the private banks. As suggestion, for better disclosure of accounting policies, the authors have suggested the followings:

(a) The statement of accounting policies of the banks should include promulgation as to compliance with the professional requirements. This will increase the quality of the financial statements to the users of information.

(b) The general accounting policies of the banks should specially describe about the matching of revenue and expenses and consolidation of accounts along with other accounting policies of this type.

(c) In the statement of major particular accounting policies, all the banks should disclose about the basis of determining the carrying amount of loans and advances on which interest is not being accrued, mode of valuation of non-banking assets and the basis of distinction between those transactions and other events that give rise to contingencies and commitments. As to valuation of investments, the banks should better follow the lower of cost or market value principle. An elaborate disclosure of Circulars relating to the basis of writing off un-collectible loans and advances is also necessary. The banks that do not disclose the following as particular accounting policies should also make such disclosure.

The limitation of the study is that no hypothesis has been tested empirically.

Chowdhury (1997) has written an article on *"A Comparative Evaluation and Rationale for Adoption of IAS 30 in Bangladesh"*. The essential objective of the study is to provide evidence that the essential purpose for adoption of IAS 30 would be to set the basic foundations of sound financial reporting for banks. Accounts cannot be truly and fairly presented unless they meet the qualitative characteristics of Financial

Statements of under standability, relevance, reliability, comparability and consistency. These qualitative characteristics cannot be properly reflected without selecting the minimum reporting requirements of IAS.

The study showed that, adoption of the standard would positively help achieve the qualitative characteristics that are necessary to reflect a true and fair view in Financial Statements of banks and harmonization of financial reporting practice in the banking sector in Bangladesh. Adoption of IAS-30 would confer relevant commensurate benefits, which result from application of IAS in general. The improvement in presentation of financial statements expected to result from application of IAS 30 have been highlighted specifically as relevant in Section 4 of this Paper. Additional benefits and 'usefulness' expected to result from adoption of IAS 30 are elucidated hereafter.

Chowdhury has found that banking business emphasizes on the principle of good client relationship through products and services and prudent stewardship of the banks monetary resources. Considerations of 'liquidity' 'solvency' and 'risk management' are most important for ensuring satisfactory performance and safeguarding the financial position - at the same time sustaining client (depositors/borrowers) confidence. Adoption of IAS 30 would facilitate management's achievement of these objectives. The users of Financial Statements of a bank need adequately understandable, relevant, reliable and comparable information which assist them in evaluating the financial position and performance of the bank and which is useful to them in making economic decisions. They also need information which gives them a better understanding of the special characteristics of the operational performance and financial position of the entity. Adoption of IAS 30 would permit Disclosures in Financial Statements of a bank which are sufficiently comprehensive to meet the overall needs of user groups.

The findings of the study indicates that adoption of IAS-30 would permit objective analysis and assessment of the financial strength of a bank's managerial and economic performance, future prospects and cash flows, banking risks, commitments and contingencies, etc. The limitation of the study is that no hypothesis has been tested empirically.

Rahman(1999) has written an article on "*The Extent of Mandatory and Voluntary Financial Disclosure by Listed Companies in Bangladesh: An Empirical Study*". The major objectives of the study are to highlight the nature of mandatory and voluntary disclosure practices of the listed companies. This paper reports on mandatory and voluntary financial disclosure practices of 20 Stock Exchange-listed manufacturing companies and relates the extent of disclosure to industry type. This study is based on secondary data. A survey of accounts was undertaken which consists of an analysis of the annual reports of the sample companies - 375 items were included in a scoring sheet, which was completed for each company. The results show that disclosure (both mandatory and voluntary) varies widely within the sample companies, and the extent of disclosure is significantly related to industry types. Companies of the Textile Sector are found to disclose significantly less information than what disclosed by companies of other sectors. The findings also indicate that the compliance with voluntary disclosure requirements is much lower compared to the compliance with mandatory disclosure requirements and that no company disclosed all mandatory information items in its annual report.

The paper has shown that disclosure is very changeable, and that, there is a significant association between the extent of disclosure and industry type. Disclosure

by companies pertaining to Pharmaceuticals and Chemicals is higher than that of companies with other industry type. Furthermore, disclosure by companies belonging to the textile industry is much lower than that of any other company. The limitation of the study is that no hypothesis has been tested empirically.

Ahmed (2000) has a study on *"Financial Reporting Practices in Banks and Financial Institutions: Implementing the New formats of Financial Statements in Compliance with IAS-30"*. This is commentary study based on secondary data. The findings of the study demonstrate that the last 15 years, the banking crises in the developing countries have been unusually frequent and severe relative to their own record compared to the preceding last three decades (Capiro and Klingebiel 1996a; 1996b; Honoban 1996; kaminsky and Reinhart 1995; Lindgren, Garcia, and Saal 1996; Sheng 1996; Sundararajan Balino 1991).

According to Lindgren, Saal and Garcia (1996) 73% of the IMF member countries experienced at least one bout of significant banking sector problems during 1980-1996 period. In Africa, Asia and transition economies of former communist countries this figure rises to more than 90%. As to the severity of banking crises and bank losses costs amounted to 10% or more of GDP in a dozen of developing countries episodes during the past 15 years. For example, Capiro and Klingebiel (1996) study reveal that there have been 67 bank crises since 1980 involving 52 developing countries. The study estimated loss as percentage of GDP, which relates to Argentina: 55%, Chile:41%, Venezuela:18%, 5 African countries:10-25%, and Israel 30%. Banking crises are costly because banks hold lion's share of financial assets of the developing economies. Gold stein and Turner (1996) calculated banks share in financial intermediation in developing countries and found India: 80%, Indonesia: 91%, Thailand: 75%, Argentina: 98%, Venezuela: 92%.

The author attempted to extend that developing countries are now larger importers, debtors, and recipients of international capital flows than they used to be, there is also an increased risk that banking crises in developing countries will have unfavorable externalities on industrial countries. The developing countries now account for approximately 45% of global output, 36% of global foreign direct investment inflows, 30% of global portfolio capital flows, 11% of global market capitalization, 12% of global issuance of international bonds, and 11-13% of global banking assets (Barth, Nolle, and Rice 1996; IFC 1996; IMF 1995; Qureshi 1996; and World bank 1997). By each of these indicators, the weight of developing countries in the global economy is considerably larger than it was 5 or 10 years ago. Banking problems tend to hit developing countries hard because banks hold the lion's share of financial assets in these countries and are by far the dominant financial intermediaries. Banks usually operate payment system, are major purchaser of government bonds and provide liquidity to fledgling securities markets. So when a bank gets into difficulties, financial system as whole quickly suffers. Banking assets, moreover, have recently been growing much faster than the size of the economies in which they operate. Accounting standards for banks make it easier to interpret information about banks and compare it against information from other banks. They thus make it easier for investors identify worthy firms and evaluate their managers. Many types of contract also rely on accounting measures to trigger certain actions. For example, the loan and bond covenants commonly include the option of immediate repayment if income or cash flow falls below specified level. Such contracts can be enforced and will be written only if accounting measures are reasonably unambiguous and if auditors can verify them. Assessing the health of banks requires reliable

information on loan classification and concentration, on the realistic valuation of collateral, on loan loss provisioning and on rules of accruing interest in the bank account when borrowers are in arrears. The accounting standards help in this regard as well. The study has also the limitation; no hypothesis has been tested empirically.

Belel (2000) has written an article "*Disclosures in Corporate Reports-A Review with Special Reference to Bangladesh*". The major objectives of this paper are to show the adequacy or inadequacy of disclosures in corporate reports, which is one of the current issues in accounting. In this paper, an attempt has been made to have an overview of the disclosure practices in Bangladesh as compared to the disclosure practices prevailing in the other countries of the world. The study reveals that disclosure practices in Bangladesh are very poor and inadequate in many respects and hence, need to be improved.

The Researcher contends that disclosure practices in Bangladesh are mostly guided by the Companies Act, 1994 Securities and Exchange Rules, 1987 and the Accounting Standards adopted by the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh. Disclosure practices are also affected by a number of other statutes e.g. Bangladesh Industrial Enterprises Nationalization Order, 1972; Bank Companies Act, 1991; Insurance Act, 1938; Income Tax ordinance, 1984 etc. However, the following major disclosures are generally required in Bangladesh:

(a) Accounting Policies

- (i) Method of valuation of fixed assets, stock and investments;
- (ii) Reasons for writing off a portion of deferred revenue expenditure;
- (iii) Method of charging depreciation and rates thereon;
- (iv) Method of conversion of foreign currencies into taka;
- (v) Changes in accounting policies;
- (vi) Methods of contract accounting.

(b) Income Statement

- (i) Establishment expenses, salaries, directors' remuneration, depreciation etc.;
- (ii) Turnover net of commission, brokerage and discount;
- (iii) Income from investments;
- (iv) Unusual Incomes and expenses;
- (v) Opening and closing stock in trade, purchases, spares consumed;
- (vi) Fuel and power;
- (vii) Salaries and wages;
- (viii) Rent, rates, taxes and insurance;
- (ix) Repairs and maintenance;
- (x) Patents, trade Mark, copyrights etc. written off;
- (xi) Auditors' remuneration;
- (xii) Interest on borrowing;
- (xiii) Provision for bad or doubtful debts and bad debts written off;
- (xiv) Provision for diminution in the value of investments;
- (xv) Provision for taxation, proposed dividend, reserves etc.

(c) Balance Sheet

- (i) Capital, reserves, debentures, sinking fund and any other funds;
- (ii) Secured and unsecured loans;
- (iii) Unclaimed dividends;
- (iv) Liabilities for acceptance,
- (v) Contingent liabilities;
- (vi) long-term loans and deferred liabilities;
- (vii) Loans from banking companies and other financial institutions and from subsidiary companies;
- (viii) loans from directors, managers and other managing agents;
- (ix) Current liabilities and provisions;
- (x) Fixed assets;
- (xi) Preliminary expenses;
- (xii) Commission, brokerage, discount etc. allowed on issue of shares;
- (xiii) Stores and spare parts, loose tools, livestock and vehicles, stock in trade etc.;
- (xiv) Book debts, bill of exchange, investments and interest accrued thereon, cash and bank balances;
- (xv) Long-term pre-payments and deferred costs;
- (xvi) Investments, Loans and

advances to subsidiary companies, controlled firms and any other associated undertakings.

(d) Directors' Report

(i) State of the company's affairs; (ii) Amount recommended as dividend; (iii) Amount transferred to reserves;

(e) Other Disclosures

(i) Capacity of industrial unit, actual production and reasons for shortfall; (ii) Mode of disposal and particulars in the case of sale of fixed assets; (iii) Comparative corresponding figures of the previous period.

Kasem (2000) had an article on "Financial Reporting Practices in Banks and Financial Institutions: Implementing the New Formats of Financial Statements in Compliance With IAS-30". The major objectives of the study are to focus that, implementing the new formats of financial statements in compliance with IAS-30 on financial reporting practices in banks and financial institutions. This is also a commentary study on an International Accounting Standard that ICAB has been trying to implement for quite sometime. The findings of the study indicate that under the Bank Companies Act, 1991, loans and advances (Balance sheet) and Income (P&L Account) were shown net of provisions. So, balance sheet and income statement, which basically did not give 'true and fair' picture of the operations of the Bank. IAS 30 on the other hand, requires the Bank to disclose the gross loans and advances and necessary provisions on the face of the balance sheet with supplementary information in the Notes to the financial statements. The author has developed the following Comparative Income Statement/Profit and Loss Account in his article.

Banking Company Act 1991	IAS 30
Income	Income
(less Provision made during the year for bad and Doubtful Debts and other Usual or Necessary Provision)	
1. Interest and Discount	Interest and similar Income
2. Commission Exchange and Brokerage	Dividend Income
3. Rents	Fees And Commission Income Gains Less Losses Arising From Dealing
Securities	Gains less losses arising from Securities
Investment	
4. Net Profit on Sale of Investment. Gold and Silver. Land Premises and Building and other Assets.	
5. Income from Non-Banking Assets and Profit from Sale of or Dealing with such Assets.	Gains less losses Arising from Dealing in Foreign Currencies
6. Other Receipts	Other Operating Income
7. Loss (if any)	
Expenditure	Expenditure
1. Interest paid and Deposits. Borrowings, etc.	Interest Expense and Similar Charges
2. Salaries, Allowances and P.F.	Fees and Commission Expense
3. Fees and Allowances for	Losses on Loans and Advances

Directors and Local Committee Members	
4. Rent, Taxes, Insurance, Lighting, etc.	General Administrative Expenses
5. Law Charges	Other Operating Expenses
6. Postage, Telegrams, Stamps	
7. Auditors Fees	
8. Repairs and Depreciation of Banking Company's Property	
9. Stationery, Printing and Advertisement	
10. Loss from Sale of Dealing on Non-Banking Assets	
11. Other Expenditure	

Here also no hypothesis has been tested empirically.

Saha and Rahman (2000) wrote an article on *"Financial Reporting Practices in Banks and Financial Institutions: Implementing The New Formats of Financial Statements in Compliance With IAS-30"*. The objective of the study is to introduce the new formats of the financial statements and its applicability in compliance with IAS 30. They mentioned that, in the context of providing financial information, all banks and financial institutions follow some legal stipulations. The statutes relating to accounting and audit of banks can be described from the public and private sector commercial banks' point of view. They introduces a circular issued by Bangladesh Bank entitled 'Amendment of First Schedule Forms of the Bank companies Act, 1991 (BRPD Circular No. 03 dated 18 April, 2000)'. Under this circular, newly amended forms have been made mandatory for all concerned banks and financial institutions since 30 March, 2000 in Bangladesh (Annexure-II). The new forms have been introduced with a view to ensuring the financial discipline in the banking sector, to minimize the unforeseeable risk, to provide true, relevant and reliable information to the depositors and shareholders and to make the financial disclosure in compliance with international standard. However, the financial statements should be easy to understand, informative and transparent. The new forms will reflect all these aspects in reporting financial information.

They attempted to extend that the banks can undertake continuous scrutiny of their performances on the basis of disclosure of their weaknesses and strengths in the financial statements and can thus remain competitive in improving the quality of financial services. The limitations of the study are: (i) They did not attempt to explain the extent of disclosure in terms of any corporate attributes such as size, listing status, audit firm, profit margin and so on. (ii) They did not find out any significant association between the extent of disclosure and the size of firms.

Azizuddin (2001) had a study on *"IAS-30 'Disclosure in the Financial Statements of Banks and Similar Financial Institutions'- Its Adoption and Implementation"*. The main objective of the study is to recapitulate the principal disclosure requirements under IAS-30. The author's explanatory requirements relating to disclosure include -

- i. accounting policies
- ii. presentation of income statement
- iii. presentation of balance sheet

- iv. market values of dealing securities and marketable investment securities if the values are different from carrying amounts in the financial statements
- v. contingencies and commitments including off-balance sheet items
- vi. maturity groupings of assets and liabilities
- vii. losses on loans and advances
- viii. general banking risks
- ix. assets pledged as securities
- x. trust activities

The study indicates that the amendments made by BB should be reviewed to remove any weakness/bottlenecks or minor errors and omissions that have crept in the first version of the amendments. The author suggested that Bangladesh Bank might constitute a small committee with representation of ICAB to further develop/extend the disclosure requirement. The limitation of the study is that its findings did not provide any support for any significant influence on the disclosure index.

Khan and Kumar (2001) has made a comprehensive study on *"IAS-30 and its Application in the Banking Sector in Bangladesh"*. The major objective of the study is to justify the IAS-30 and its application in the Banking sector in Bangladesh. It is a descriptive study based on secondary data (reports) such as IAS-30: Task Force Report (unpublished), 2000, Scheduled Banks Statistics, Bank Companies Act, 1991, Basle Committee Report, IAS-30 and 33. To ensure more transparency in accounting system and disclosure of important accounting policies of banks and financial institutions in Bangladesh, the Central Bank issued a circular (BRPD Circular No. 3/2000 dated 18/4/2000) for adoption IAS -30 (International Accounting Standard-30). It brings some changes in the related sections of the Bank Companies Act, 1991. In this paper, The authors try to make focus on the extents of disclosure of financial information as per newly adopted form of financial statements for banks and financial institutions and the problems faced by the users of traditional form of financial statements. However, the suggestions of Basle Committee in this regard, important features of IAS-30 and new guidelines, problems in implementing IAS-30, etc. have also been covered here.

Legal bottlenecks and absence of proper guidelines and instructions no more exist with the circulation of BRPD Circular No. 3/2000. The paper has shown that the banks will be in a position to prepare their financial statements in accordance with the new standard so as to enable the users to have fair, transparent and reliable information. If we want to ensure discipline and accountability in the accounting system we have no other option but to go for implementation of IAS-30 guidelines. The limitation of the study is that it did not attempt to explain the extent of disclosure in terms of any corporate attributes such as size, listing status, audit firm, profit margin and so on.

Haque (2002) has written an article on *"A study on Published Annual Accounting Report Corporate Governance and Oversight Functions in Bangladesh and some other countries 2000-2002 (Financial listed companies)"* under the World Bank Financial Project of "Development of Accounting and Auditing Standards in Bangladesh". The major objective of the study is to evaluate the degree of compliance with IAS adopted by ICAB and some other good governance practices in other countries. The study is based on both primary and secondary data. In the survey references were made to better quality annual reports from multinational companies in Bangladesh and some other countries, such as Sri Lanka, India and UK. Annual reports from

these countries covered issues such as corporate strategies, human resource and environmental concerns more elaborately and understandable for readers of annual accounting reports.

The major findings of the study are that the high magnitude of the crisis faced in USA, UK and other countries corporate governance and accounting related matters have been receiving due attention from all concerned so that workable solutions are found out within the legal and administrative systems. IAS is practiced, albeit in different levels, in a handful of countries in the world. Compliance to IAS is not going to be the panacea for all the problems of corporate governance. However, under WTO there will be greater pressure on all member countries to adopt IAS and good corporate governance practices. Another important lesson was that whatever reform measures are planned and how large pay packages might be offered to attract qualified persons to oversee both accounting firms and industry, personal character and integrity of the candidates will ultimately determine effectiveness of oversight functions.

The survey found various inadequacies in annual accounting reports and there was lack of uniformity in several required disclosures. For example, IAS-1 requires statement of accounting policies in one place. While companies stated accounting policies in one place, number of such policies varied between 5 to 17. Variation in accounting policies can make financial analysis difficult and meaningless for comparative purposes. The author found that most of the reports were poor in quality of presentation and production. The researcher finds out that corporate governance and accounting disclosure related topics received much more importance in those countries than got in Bangladesh.

Recommendations of this report are that GOB, SEC and ICAB should work closely to establish a high powered committee such as the public Accountability Board in the USA to oversee accounting and corporate governance related matters and establish Audit Committees to oversee auditing and revise audit fees as per guidelines of ICAB. Arrangement to appoint non-executive directors to boards as are being done for banks. Only professional in accounting, finance, management and economics are to be placed as non-executive directors. Like in the UK non-executives may be put as chairmen of boards and all of them should be due compensated for their services. The limitation of the study is that no hypothesis has been tested empirically.

Bhuiyan and Kamal (2003) have carried out a study on *"Standardization of Accounting and Financial Reporting Practices in the Banking Sector in Bangladesh: An Evaluation of the implementation of IAS-30 by the Banks in the Private Sector"*. The objective of the study is to evaluate whether the commercial banks of Bangladesh follow the underlying standards regarding the preparation of their financial statements. In their study, they will also make an evaluation of the implementation and impact of IAS-30 on accounting and reporting by the banking companies in the country. Their study was pursued to know details about how a bank present their financial statements, whether they comply with the existing rules and regulations as well as relevant IAS and Bangladesh Accounting Standards (BASs). Based on their little access with the examined banks, their evaluation of the financial statements of banks is not very extensive. Their little observation reveals that the accounting and reporting in our banking sector need up-gradation, which may be attained by the proper implementation of the relevant standards, IAS-30 would be a great help in this respect. Proper accounting and reporting of the financial facts help to develop transparency and accountability, which are very essential for the good governance or

efficient corporate governance in the banking sector also. They suggest that relevant authority should be more conscious in monitoring the implementation of IAS-30 in the banking sector for better accountability and transparency.

The gist of the recommendations of their study was that a monitoring authority or cell must be formed to monitor the implementation of the IAS-30 in the banking sector in Bangladesh. Workshops should be organized for the auditors to audit about the compliance of the IAS-30 by the banks. The accounting staff of the banking sector should be trained to account in accordance with the IAS and other relevant regulations and an appraisal and reward punishment should be ensured for the compliance and non-compliance of the IAS-30 and other relevant regulations for the banking sector. No hypothesis has been tested empirically in this present study.

Haque and Islam (2005) in their article entitled "*Compliance of IAS 30 by Bank Companies of Bangladesh*" have tried to provide the quality information through the financial statements, which is comparable by the global users. It is very crucial to bring uniformity in the accounting practices all over the world. The main objectives of the study are to examine the issue of compliance of IAS-30 by the bank companies of Bangladesh and to find out whether there are statistical differences in compliance of IAS-30 between Publicly Traded Banks and Nationalized Banks. This study reveals that the banks of our country follow the IAS 30 requirements as far as possible. This study also finds that there is no significant difference in terms of compliance of IAS-30 between the publicly traded and nationalized banks. That means all the sample banks try to follow similar items needed to comply with the international standard in order to provide accountability and transparency in financial reporting, which ensure maximum disclosure of the relevant, reliable and useful information to the interested user groups. The limitation of their study is that its findings did not provide any support for any significant influence on the disclosure index.

Malek (2005) has studied on the "*A Comparative Analysis of Commercial Banking Performance in Bangladesh*". The main objective of the study is to provide evidence that the banking sector in Bangladesh is different from the banking sector as seen in other developed countries. In this study simple statistical tool such as average, is used to judge how they are performing within themselves in the area of deposit collection, foreign business and over all financial result. According to the author's view the banking sector is one of the major service sector in Bangladesh economy, which is divided into four categories - Nationalized Bank, Local Private Bank, Specialized Financial Institutions and Foreign Banks. Their objectives, ownership pattern, mode of operation and other also differ from each other based on the category of banking to which they belong. For this study only the performance of Nationalized commercial Bank, Local Private commercial Banks and Foreign Commercial Banks operating during 1999 to 2002, are taken into consideration. The result shows that though majority of total assets, total foreign business and total deposits are held by the local private and nationalized banks but foreign banks outperformed other in performance. In this study no hypothesis has been tested empirically.

Ali, Khan, Fatima and Masud (2008) provide a useful survey of the attitudes of individual respondents on the various aspects of Bangladeshi annual corporate reports. They analyzed the responses of 25 individual investors and found firstly, British American Tobacco (BAT) Bangladesh Co. Ltd makes very few disclosures on corporate governance on a voluntary basis and secondly, the user groups of the

annual reports are in favor of such disclosure. The researchers further found that the current disclosures are not ample in evaluating the goal of corporate governance.

4.3 Review of Related Study in Abroad

Most of these studies are country specific, although there are studies often consider the 'adequacy' of the disclosure of information based on a checklist of desirable mandatory and voluntary items.

Barrett (1977) has studied the extent of disclosure in the corporate annual reports of large companies in seven countries. The countries studied were the US, the UK, Japan, the Netherlands, Germany, Sweden and France. He has surveyed 103 companies as the total sample with 15 companies each from the USA, Sweden, Germany, France, Japan the UK and 13 companies from the Netherlands. The market capitalization level of the companies on 28 September 1973 has been used as the primary criterion for selecting the sample companies. Seventeen items of financial disclosure were employed in the disclosure index. Weights were assigned to the first 12 items of the disclosure index on a range of '0' to '4' based on the weights employed in different studies. Barrett used his personal judgment and the first twelve weights to decide weights to be assigned to the remaining five items. Each annual report was then scored against the disclosure index both with the without weights. His study provided evidence that the extent of financial disclosure in the annual reports of large companies in the USA was greater, on an average, than he found in the annual reports of major companies in Japan, Sweden, the Netherlands, Germany and France during 1963 to 1972 period. His result was consistent with the belief that there is a relationship between the extent and quality of financial disclosure and the degree of efficiency of a national equity market.

Firth (1978) in his research on the "*Consensus of the perceived importance of disclosure of individual items in corporate annual reports*", has tried to assess the information requirements from the point of UK users. The basic research instrument consisted of a questionnaire containing seventy-five items that were, or could be disclosed in a company annual report. The questionnaire was sent to a sample of 750 users of financial information. It included 250 financial directors; 250 qualified accountant working in audit firms; 120 financial analysts working for stockbrokers and investment organizations; and 130 loan officers of major banks and finance houses in London. Respondents were instructed to evaluate the importance of each item using a five point Likert scale. Six hypotheses were formulated suggesting no significant difference between any two-user groups (the possible combinations of four groups taking two at a time). The hypotheses were tested by *t* statistics to measure the significance of differences in-group means. Hypothesis one, dealing finance directors and auditors, was rejected for 23 of the 75 items indicating that the two groups of users are in significant disagreement about the perceived importance of 23 items. Similarly, results of hypothesis two, dealing with finance directors and financial analysts, showed that they disagreed about 42 items. In the same way, it is found that finance directors and loan officers disagreed on 49 items, auditors and financial analysts disagree on 46 items, and finally, financial analysts and loan officers significantly disagreed on 14 items.

Anderson (1981) also recognized the need for research in this area and focused on institutional investors in Australia. He sought, primarily, to discover their perceptions about the importance of annual corporate reports to their decision making process by analyzing the responses of 188 institutional investors. Anderson

(1981) found that Australian investors relied mostly on the annual report when making their investment decisions followed by visits to the companies. Regarding the annual corporate report itself, the most readable sections of the annual report were the balance sheet, profit and loss account, notes to the accounts, and the chairman's statement respectively. The profit and loss account, however, was perceived to be more important than the balance sheet. However, the author failed to perform any statistical test to determine whether there is a significant difference between the users' usage of the annual report sections on the one hand and the perceived importance of such sections on the other hand. Anderson (1981) also documents the external users' desire (i.e., 72 per cent) for additional information to be provided in the annual corporate report such as information about the company's product, current value of long-term assets, and remuneration of directors.

Kahl and Belkaoui (1981) have pioneered the research on *"Bank Annual Report Disclosure Adequacy Internationally"*. The major objectives of the study are to highlight the nature of disclosure adequacy of banks in an international setting. The study investigates the overall extent of disclosure by banks located in 18 countries. Disclosure adequacy is measured in this study by the extent to which 30-selected information items are presented in the annual reports. The 1975 annual reports of the 70 commercial banks were evaluated on the basis of the response score assigned to each of the informational items in the disclosure index.

In their study Kahl and Belkaoui have found that the differences in disclosure adequacy exist internationally, at least for the countries included in their sample, with considerable variability in extent, and with US banks definitely the leaders. In addition, the three accounting model hypothesis that has been empirically supported for non-financial firms is not supported by their data on banks. Further the evidence in their study supported the positive correlation between asset size and extent of disclosure, although less strongly than might have been expected. Finally, the information items used in their study to measure disclosure adequacy, when classified according to the consensus between producers and users of bank financial statements, indicate ten items of low consensus, which are also subject to much current debate and controversy. These items obviously merit more research effort.

The authors have suggested that financial managers in banks should focus their attention on these controversial items when formulating and/or revising their disclosure policy and financial managers of non-financial firms might also consider these same points when taking disclosure policy decisions.

Chow and Boren (1987) studied the extent of voluntary financial disclosure practices of Mexican corporations and sought to relate the extent of disclosure to three firm characteristics, viz. firm size, financial leverage, and proportion of assets in place. They selected 52 listed manufacturing companies for the year 1982 from the *Mexican Government's 1982 Official Gazette*. They developed a disclosure index consisting of 89 items of information. Using a seven-point scale, they judged the importance of the items considered to be significant from the viewpoint of 106 loan officers of 16 Mexican Banks. They found that the extent of voluntary disclosure increased with firm size being measured as the market value of equity plus book value of debt. However, they did not find any significant association between financial leverage and assets in place and the extent of voluntary disclosure.

Anderson and Epstein (1995) further extended their research by providing a useful investigation on Australia. Unlike the Anderson (1981) study, which specifically focused on Australian institutional investors, the Anderson and Epstein (1995) study

was more concerned with individual investors' usage of annual corporate reports. Their findings revealed that the annual corporate reports came third, after stockbrokers' advice and financial newspapers and magazines, as a basis for investment decision of Australian individual investors. Nevertheless, the vast majority of their respondents (i.e., 72 per cent) perceived annual corporate reports to be of only moderate use. Regarding the use of the annual report, the authors highlight the directors' report to be the most thoroughly read followed by the income statement. Nevertheless, their respondents did perceive the income statement to be more useful than the directors' report in making an investment decision. Arguably, Anderson and Epstein (1995) did not statistically determine whether the difference between the pattern of readership of the annual reports' sections and the perceived usefulness of such sections is of any significance in the Australian environment. Respondents had also expressed a desire for the simplification and more explanation of the balance sheet, statement of cash flow, and the income statement. Finally, the authors highlight the Australian investors' demand for additional disclosure in the annual reports; such as pending litigation, unasserted claims, management audit, and information on change of auditor.

Abu-Nassar and Rutherford (1996) in another Middle Eastern environment, Jordan, undertook a study to discover the view of external users of annual corporate reports. The authors targeted different groups of external users, namely individual shareholders, institutional shareholders, bank loan officers, stockbrokers, and academics. Their sample comprised of 224 respondents and all of their analyses are of a univariate type. In terms of the usage of the annual report, Abu-Nassar and Rutherford (1996) found bank loan officers to be the heaviest users of the annual reports in Jordan while individual shareholders and academics were found to be the least. They also found the income statement and balance sheet to be the most widely read parts of the annual corporate report by all the users. The authors documented the low degree of users' satisfaction about many qualitative characteristics of corporate reports in Jordan. In terms of the importance of the various sources of corporate information, Abu-Nassar and Rutherford (1996) argue the annual corporate report to be the most important source of information for all user groups. The only exception being the bank loan officers who indicated that the most important source of information to them was to personally visit companies followed by an independent examination of the annual report itself.

Marston and Robson (1997) wrote an article on *"Financial Reporting in India: Changes in Disclosure over the Period 1982 to 1990"*. This study started with a brief examination of the main factors that may affect Indian financial reporting and disclosure: the legal environment, the Indian professional accounting environment and the international accounting standards. The research instrument used was a weighted or un-weighted disclosure index, which included both voluntary and mandatory items. The authors examined the disclosure requirements paying particular attention to the 17 items listed in Barrett's index of disclosure, which formed the focus of the empirical work. Disclosure was measured at the beginning (1982/83) and end (1989/90) of the selected period for a sample of 29 large Indian companies.

The authors have tried to determine that disclosure level increased over time and that in both periods disclosure was positively associated with company size. Reasons for improved disclosure included increased compliance with accounting standards (which were advisory at the time of the survey) and an increase in the disclosures

required by accounting standards. It may be that over the period of the survey that more companies decided to exhibit best practice by complying with the Indian accounting standards given that they would soon be mandatory anyway.

This study has two main limitations. The first major problem is the small number of annual reports that were obtained for this study. It was not considered practical to attempt to enlarge the sample because of the difficulty in obtaining sets of accounts from such a long time ago (1982/83). The other limitation is the use of the rather dated Barrett index, it might have been preferable to use or adapt a disclosure index from a more recent study or to attempt to devise an index to suit the Indian context in the 1980s. However, given the small data set and the fact that the index produced the expected results in testing it was decided that this study should be deemed to be of an exploratory nature and that a future study should attempt to sample a wider population and develop a better disclosure index.

Hossain (1998) has carried out a study in his Ph.D., dissertation entitled *"Disclosure of Financial Information in Developing Countries: A comparative study of non-financial companies in India, Pakistan and Bangladesh"*. The major objectives of his study was to examine empirically the association between a number of corporate attributes and levels of disclosure in corporate annual reports of listed non-financial companies in three developing countries, India, Pakistan and Bangladesh. The perceived importance of a selected list of information items to four categories of users (i.e. bank loan officers, financial analysts, stock exchange members and professional chartered accountants) is also examined and the determinants of audit delay and audit fees are also ascertained. A disclosure index comprising 94 items of information which are expected to be disclosed in corporate annual reports in the sample companies has been developed. Both weighted and unweighted disclosure indices were applied to the corporate annual reports for a sample of 78 Bangladeshi companies, 80 Indian companies and 103 Pakistani companies for the 1992-1993.

In his study, the association between the extent of disclosure and various corporate characteristics was examined using multiple linear regression models. It was hypothesised in the study that for the sample companies in these three developing countries, corporate variables reflecting size (assets and sales), profitability (rate of return on assets and net profit margin), debt equity ratio, presence of debenture in debt, international link of the audit firm, industry type, subsidiary of a multinational company would be positively associated with the extent of disclosure. In his study, it was found for the Bangladeshi companies that size (total assets) and subsidiary of a multinational company were significantly associated with the extent of disclosure. In the case of Pakistani companies, the results showed that assets in place, size (total assets) and presence of debentures in debt structure were significantly associated with the extent of disclosure. The results for Indian companies, showed that extent of disclosure was significantly related to presence of debentures in debt structure, industry type, size sales) and rate of return on total assets. No significant differences were found for the weighted disclosure index and unweighted disclosure index.

It was found in his study that the mean disclosure level of Pakistani companies was greater than that of Bangladeshi and Indian companies. The average disclosure level of Indian companies found to be slightly lower than the Pakistani companies. However, there is a significant difference between Indian and Pakistani companies and Bangladeshi companies. The mean disclosure level of Bangladeshi companies was much lower than those of other two countries. Among 96 questionnaire items,

the one-way ANOVA model for variance tests showed a high degree of consensus among Bangladeshi respondents (89.80%), Indian respondents (94.90%) and Pakistani respondents (90.82%). A majority of the respondents in India, Pakistan and Bangladesh perceived that the published annual reports in the sample country were not adequate and reliable.

The analysis of audit delay showed that for Indian, Bangladeshi and Pakistani sample companies, the variable of a subsidiary of a multinational company was significantly associated with audit delay. The results for Indian companies also showed that audit delay was significantly related to debt equity ratio and size (total assets). The results of audit fees determinants suggest that for Bangladesh and India only size (sales) were significantly positively associated with audit fees levels, while in the case of Pakistan size (sales) and a subsidiary of a multinational company variable were found to be positively associated with audit fees. The study suggests that the audit services market in India, Pakistan and Bangladesh may have some interesting characteristics but further study is needed. The study examined only one year's financial statement, is the limitation of the study.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper reviewed many empirical studies of the perceived importance of information of different groups of users as well as preparers of corporate annual reports in Bangladesh and abroad. The above-mentioned literature survey states that financial reporting in Bangladesh is very poor. Most of the organizations including banks follow mainly the legal requirements in preparing their financial statements. But the forms as prescribed by the relevant laws for the preparations of financial statements are outdated and inadequate to ensure the desired disclosure. Scope of the present study is vast and so far we know, no one of the studies reviewed was able to include as large number of the different commercial banks as sampled by the present researchers. Not only, most of the existing studies criticized the legal requirements, but also they failed to suggest specific change or modifications to update the forms of preparing the financial statements of banks. Above all, time is a great factor, which along with other factors can distinguish the findings of the present researchers from those of the others.

From the above review of related literature it can be concluded that there is enough scope for understanding this sort of study of the banking sector of Bangladesh due to lack of broad based research study done earlier in this vital field. As a project it can be undertaken for a detailed study '*Compliance of financial disclosure in corporate annual reports of banking sector of Bangladesh*'. This study has considered the limitations of the aforesaid studies and has to try to have good lessons from their data analytical techniques, data collection tools, statistical variable used etc.

Reference

- Abu-Nassar and Rutherford (1996) "Corporate disclosure policy and analyst behavior in Jordan" *The Accounting Review*, (10), pp. 467-492.
- Accounting Standards, Statements of Financial Accounting Concepts 1-6, FASB, McGraw-Hill Book Co., 1986.
- Agarwal, "Disclosure in Company Accounts", Hind Law Publishers, 1995.
- Ahmed (2000) "Financial Reporting Practices in Banks and Financial Institutions: Implementing the New formats of Financial Statements in Compliance with IAS-30", *The Bangladesh Accountant*, July-September, 2000, p-21-26.
- Akter and Hoque (1993) "Disclosure Practices in Bangladesh: A Case Study of the Banking Sector", *Dhaka University Journal of Business Studies*, Vol. 14(2), 1993, p-29-42.
- Ali, Khan, Fatima and Masud (2008) "Voluntary Corporate Governance Reporting in Annual Reports: A Study of an MNC", *ASA University Review*, Vol. 2 No. 2, July-Dec., pp. 61-75.
- Anderson (1981) "The usefulness of Accounting and other information Disclosed Corporate Annual Reports to Institutional Investors in Australia", *Accounting and Business Research*, Autumn, pp. 259-265.
- Anderson and Epstein (1995) "The Pricing of Audit Services: Further Evidence from the Canadian Market", *Accounting and Business research*, Volume 24, No.25, pp. 195-207.
- Azizuddin (2001) "IAS-30 'Disclosure in the Financial Statements of Banks and Similar Financial Institutions'- Its Adoption and Implementation" *The Bangladesh Accountant*, October-December, 2001, p-29-41.
- Bangladesh Standards on Auditing (BSA), ICAB, 2004.
- Barrett (1977) "The Extent of Disclosure in Annual Report of Large Companies in Seven Countries", *The International Journal of Accounting Education and Research*, Vol. 13, No. 2, pp. 1-25.
- Bhuiyan and Kamal (2003) "Standardization of Accounting and Financial Reporting Practices in the Banking Sector in Bangladesh: An Evaluation of the implementation of IAS-30 by the Banks in the Private Sector", *Dhaka University Journal of Business Studies*, Volume XXIV No.2 December 2003, p-25-37.
- Chow and Boren (1987) "Voluntary Financial Disclosure by Mexican Corporation", *The Accounting Review*, pp. 533-541.
- Chowdhury (1997) "A Comparative Evaluation and Rationale for Adoption of IAS 30 in Bangladesh", *The Bangladesh Accountant*, July-September, 1997, p-129-141.
- Firth (1978) "A study of consensus of the perceived importance of Disclosure of Individual Items in Corporate Annual Reports", *International Journal of Accounting*, Fall, pp.57-70.
- Haque (2002) "A study on Published Annual Accounting Report Corporate Governance and Oversight Functions in Bangladesh and some other countries 2000-2002 (Financial listed companies)", The World Bank Financed Project "Development of Accounting and Auditing Standards in Bangladesh", (IDF Grant No. 27304), ICAB.
- Haque and Islam (2005) "Compliance of IAS 30 by Bank Companies of Bangladesh", *The Cost and Management*, May-June, 2005, p-24-27.
- Hossain (1998) "Disclosure of Financial Information in Developing Countries: A comparative study of non-financial companies in India, Pakistan and Bangladesh", Ph.D. dissertation, School of Accounting and Finance, Victoria University of Manchester, UK, July 1998.
- Inchausti (1997) "The influence of company characteristics and accounting regulations on information disclosed by Spanish Firms", *The European Accounting Review*, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 45-68.
- Islam and Pramanik (1996) "Disclosure of Accounting Policies: A Study of the Commercial Banks in Bangladesh", unpublished research work.
- Kahl and Belkaoui (1981) "Bank Annual Report Disclosure Adequacy Internationally", *Accounting and Business Research*, Summer 1981, p-189-195.
- Kahl and Belkaoui (1981) "Bank annual report Disclosures Adequacy Internationally", *Accounting and Business Research*, Summer.

- Kasem (2000) "Financial Reporting Practices in Banks and Financial Institutions: Implementing the New Formats of Financial Statements in Compliance With IAS-30", *The Bangladesh Accountant*, July-September, 2000, p-18-20.
- Khan and Kumar (2001) "IAS-30 and its Application in the Banking Sector in Bangladesh", *Bank Parikrama*, Volume XXVI, No.1, March 2001, p-5-21.
- Malek (2005) "A Comparative Analysis of Commercial Banking Performance in Bangladesh", *The Cost And Management*, May-June, 2005, p-2-9.
- Marston and Robson (1997) "Financial Reporting in India: Changes in Disclosure over the Period 1982 to 1990", *Asia-Pacific Journal of Accounting*, June 1997, p-109-135.
- Mautz and May, "Financial Disclosure in Competitive Economy", Financial Executives Research Foundation, New York, 1978, p-6.
- Porwal, "Accounting Theory An Introduction", Second Edition, 1996, Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Ltd., New Delhi.
- Rahman(1999) "The Extent of Mandatory and Voluntary Financial Disclosure by Listed Companies in Bangladesh: An Empirical Study", *Dhaka University Journal of Business Studies*, Vol. 20(1), 1999, p-189-208.
- Saha and Rahman (2000) "Financial Reporting Practices in Banks and Financial Institutions: Implementing The New Formats of Financial Statements in Compliance With IAS-30". *The Bangladesh Accountant*, July-September, 2000, p-11-17.